
A Comparative Study of Old and Recent Riyadh Neighborhood Forms Using Objective and Subjective Measures

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Abstract

The paper sets out to compare old city and more recently developed neighborhood forms in Riyadh. Both objective quantitative and subjective qualitative measures of neighborhood forms were assessed for both neighborhood types. The first consists of analyzing GIS-derived objective neighborhood form indicators such as density, land use mix and street network patterns. The second consists of measuring the sense of community among neighborhood residents that such a form might foster. Survey questionnaire interviews were used to assess resident perception and how strong is the sense of community within the neighborhood. The results indicated that old city (*Deerah*) neighborhoods tend to be more compact, with more mixed and diversified land uses and more interconnected street networks than the more recently built neighborhood forms according to the conventional suburban development (CSD) precepts. It was also found that older neighborhood forms perform far better in fostering a stronger sense of community among its residents than do modern neighborhood forms.

Keywords: *Sense of Community; Neighborhood form; New Urbanism; Riyadh; Urban Sprawl; GIS.*

1. Introduction

Neighborhood form has often been evaluated in the literature using either objective or subjective measures. Objective measures rely more on the physical form of the neighborhood and the attributes of its built environment. This approach has led to discuss neighborhood form either in terms of urban sprawl or urban compactness (Ewing, 1997; Galster et al., 2001; Neuman, 2005). With the rise of the modern movement in architecture and planning and the widespread of the private car use, there has been an upswing of sprawling neighborhood forms all over the place. To curb the pervasive impacts of urban sprawl, many urban planners advocated the return to traditional urban landscapes to dwell their inspiration for more compact neighborhood forms (Krier, 1978, Duany and Plater-Zyberk, 1992).

Subjective approaches to neighborhood form measurement tend to insist more on evaluating the relationship between sense of community and neighborhood form as expressed in the physical characteristics of the built environment. New Urbanists contend that neighborhood form design is an important media or stimulant to foster greater sense of community. They assume that pedestrian friendly streets tend to foster a greater sense of community than do their counterparts characterized as pedestrian hostile streets. Street walkability is important attribute of neo-traditional neighborhood forms advocated by new urbanists. The argument goes that they encourage casual spontaneous encounters, social interactions and neighboring which help entice relationships between residents and a feeling of neighborliness and belonging to the area and hence building mutual trust and commitment to the community. These characteristics are important to convey a sense of neighborhood among community members. Many scholars like

Leyden (2003) and Lund (2002) have argued that walkable areas tend to facilitate opportunities for residents to meet frequently, interact and socialize with each other which at the end fosters a sense of community among them.

Lund argued that sense of community tends to be stronger in traditional neighborhood settings as they have more street connectivity and mixed uses which encourage more walking and hence more informal contacts among residents (Lund, 2002). These conclusions resonates with what new urbanists suggest that walkable environments enhance sense of community as they allow more social interactions and informal encounters to take place. Again, Leyden (2003) and Cattell (2001) suggest that mixed land uses and interconnected street networks tend to promote walkability and thus increase sense of neighborhood.

On the contrary, sprawl-oriented neighborhood forms designed in line with the conventional suburban development (CSD) precepts tend to have pedestrian unfriendly streets as a result of the excessive use of the private car. Such neighborhood forms tend to inhibit social interaction and neighboring as they constrain street walkability and hence casual encounters. Residents of such neighborhoods are often confined either in their cars or inside their homes or office works. They have therefore, fewer opportunities to meet and socialize with people in the public street. A neighborhood form that is pedestrian-friendly is expected to be associated with higher sense of neighborhood community as it provides more opportunities for casual social contact and socialization among members of the neighborhood community. Many scholars argue that walkable streets and quality public open spaces tend to foster more opportunities for social interactions and spontaneous encounters among neighborhood residents. Such social encounters and interactions would lead to a stronger sense of neighborhood community and reinforce social involvement and effective participation in local affairs (Leyden, 2003; Talen, 1999).

Duany and Plater-Zyberk (1992) argued that the main flaw of conventional suburban development CSD consists mainly in its insidious social effect more than its deficiency on aesthetic and environmental grounds (Duany and Plater-Zyberk, 1992). According to the view of New Urbanists the sense of neighborhood community follows the physical form of its built environment. The essence of New Urbanists attempt is to create a sense of neighborhood community through neighborhood form design. This sense of neighborhood community was the main goal of Clarence Perry's neighborhood unit concept.

Riyadh has known two types of neighborhood forms. A traditional form in the old city locally known as *Deerah*, and recently, some modern neighborhood forms built in line with the precepts of conventional suburban development (CSD). The emergence of these modern forms followed the oil economic boom of the seventies and the concomitant staggering pace of construction. If the old city neighborhoods were usually of compact, smaller size and traditional forms, the modern neighborhoods were mainly of sprawling single-use form with automobile-dependent and leap-frog configurations. They were in total contrast with those of the traditional old city neighborhoods.

2. Definition of Neighborhood Form

Earlier definitions of neighborhood form tend to focus more on aesthetic aspects and physical appearance. Whereas recent definitions put more emphasis on the sense of community and place that such a form might foster. The former view insists that the physical character of a neighborhood and its design layout determine its form (Sutton, 1971). Kevin Lynch for instance,

delineates the good neighborhood form in terms of its street network pattern, lot configuration and design layout, block size and shape, and public open space arrangements (Lynch: 1981). Handy also defines the neighborhood form in terms of land use patterns, street network and physical design layout (Handy, 1996). Neighborhood form is therefore seen more as a geographical construct with an identifiable form within a physically bounded area.

The recent view however, holds the idea of neighborhood form as a social construct with a whole set of shared values and community ties enticing neighborhood residents together through social interaction and neighboring. The advocates of this view expands the notion of neighborhood form beyond its geographical and physical limits to encompass the extent of social neighboring and interactions. These advocates are often members of the New Urbanism Movement. They give more weight to human relations and residents' socialization as determinants of sense of community and belonging to place. Chaskin argued that the neighborhood form is not only a physical construct but a social construct as well (Chaskin, 2006). In her review of the literature, Moudon and her colleagues stressed the importance of what a neighborhood form evokes in terms of community feelings and a shared sense of place, human contact and social interaction (Moudon et al., 2006).

New urbanist neighborhood forms aim to foster sense of community by increasing walking, mixing land uses and diversifying housing, strengthening personal and social ties and increasing people's socialization. Neighborhood form definition is therefore, not restricted to good physical design or appealing aesthetics but is extended to include larger social underpinnings such as creating healthy social communities, empowering neighborhood residents, developing local economies and preserving environmental quality.

3. Measures of Neighborhood Form

Neighborhood form measurements vary to a great extent in the literature depending on the definition adopted for the concept. For those who insist on physical design and aesthetic formal features, they tend to use urban form variables as measures of neighborhood form. Such variables are mainly objective measures of land use, block size, street length and housing density (Herold et al., 2002; Huang et al., 2007). For others who give weight to subjective measures, they tend to include socioeconomic indicators such as population size, density, residents' demographics and measures of "sense of community", walkability and social interaction and neighboring (Frenkel and Ashkenazi, 2008; Kasanko et al., 2006; Tsai, 2005; Talen, 1999; Chaskin 1986).

More recent studies tend to combine both objective and subjective measures to evaluate neighborhood form. Using GIS tools, Song and Knaap (2003) assessed street network features, density, land use diversity, accessibility and walkability as a proxy to evaluate neighborhood form (Song and Knaap, 2003; Song, 2005). In his extensive study of sustainable neighborhood forms, Jabareen (2006) and Song (2005) view neighborhood form through the lenses of sustainability and smart growth principles. They developed measures like compactness, sustainable transport, density, mixed land uses, diversity, passive solar design, and greening as main determinants of sustainable neighborhood form.

Relying on the capabilities offered by geographic information systems (GIS) tools, Nina Schwarz (2010) used some 27 landscape metrics and 18 socioeconomic-based indicators to measure either sprawl-oriented or compact neighborhood forms of 231 European cities. Schneider and Woodcock (2008) quantified sprawling neighborhood forms using size or spatial

extent of sealed urban area. Huang et al. (2007) developed a compactness index and a centrality index among many other parameters like centrality, porosity and density to describe compact neighborhood forms by drawing comparisons between 77 cities worldwide.

Using GIS data computation tools, Allen (2001) developed a set of indicators called INDEX to measure urban neighborhood form. INDEX uses measures of density, nuclearity, centrality, residential proximity to retail and industrial uses, and accessibility to parks, shops, and transit. Hess and Moudon (2000) have developed measures of street connectivity as a specific feature of neighborhood form, whereas Southworth (2003) used street pattern design and livability to capture such form. Similarly, Krizek (2003) shifted the focus on the association between urban form and transportation network, while Duany (2001) developed the idea of the “transect” to describe neighborhood form.

As far as the measurement of the “sense of neighborhood community” is concerned, many scholars used tool measures borrowed from sociological fields. The Sense of Community Index (SCI) developed by McMillan and Chavis (1986) adopted four elements: membership, influence, meeting needs, and a shared emotional connection to predict how strong is the sense of community among neighborhood residents. It was widely used as a valid instrument measure. Since walkable neighborhoods tend to foster social interaction among residents, the sense of neighborhood community is therefore believed to have a strong association with pedestrian-friendly environments. The argument was that neighborhood form that offers more opportunities for informal social contacts and spontaneous interactions in public open spaces like streets and squares, tend to foster a greater sense of neighborhood community among residents (Leyden, 2003; Talen, 1999). Young et al. (2004) used six predictors to capture this sense of neighborhood community. They are trusting neighbors, having friends among neighbors, communal help, feelings of mutual respect, involvement in local issues, and attachment to the neighborhood area. Promoting open walkable spaces of quality play a key role in enhancing this sense of neighborhood community. It is crucial therefore to encourage pedestrianism to increase the likelihood of social interactions among neighborhood residents.

4. The Study Methodology

This study is undertaken under the contention that urban neighborhood form is best determined by both objective and subjective attributes. It is therefore necessary to measure objective urban form variables (density, land use mix, street network patterns, etc.) as well as subjective qualities of urban neighborhood form such as the sense of community, social interaction and neighboring that such a form may generate.

The present paper sets out to examine differences in old and modern neighborhood forms in Riyadh. The term “neighborhood form” is used here to refer to both the physical neighborhood form and the sense of neighborhood community that binds its residents to each other and to their place. That is, the buildings, streets, lots, spaces, sense of neighboring, socialization and all other elements that make up the neighborhood form. The objective measurement variables were extracted from Riyadh City’s databases in geographic information systems (GIS). These objective measures of neighborhood attributes include count, area, distance and ratio measures of individual and groups of destinations. In this regard, ArcGIS Spatial Analyst tools were applied to create useful information from the City’s databases provided by Al-Riyadh Development Authority (ADA). They were also used to perform different analyses and calculations of lot and block densities, street densities and lengths, Service areas were used to

visualize and measure accessibility. A 500 meters threshold around some neighborhood services like schools, place of worship, or gardens, was used to determine how many dwelling units are covered.

Subjective perceptual measures were drawn from survey analysis undertaken in some selected neighborhoods in both old and recently developed Riyadh City. The neighborhoods were taken to cover a range of socioeconomic characteristics of residents (low, medium and high). The McMillan & Chavis (1986) “*Sense of Community Index*” (SCI) was adopted as a measurement instrument for sense of neighborhood community.

The city core traditional neighborhood forms with their traditional compact structure were set against the more recently built neighborhood forms which often adopt a conventional suburban development configuration. Figure 1 below shows Riyadh city with its old city neighborhoods or traditional core known as *Deerah* and the more recently developed Riyadh or Modern Riyadh.

Riyadh City is subdivided into six sectors each of which is composed of a number of neighborhoods (Figure 1). The first sector contains the traditional core whose neighborhood forms tend to adopt a more compact configuration (Figure 2) as opposed to the more recently built neighborhoods in the remaining sectors which are usually characterized of sprawling, lower density, scattered and commercial strip development.

As far as neighborhood form objective measures are concerned, the values were computed for each neighborhood and the mean values were then calculated for comparisons between the old traditional neighborhood forms and the more recent modern forms.

Figure 1: Map (left) of Riyadh City with its six sectors as determined by Ar-Riyadh Development Authority (ADA). The figure to the right shows a zoom view on the central sector (Sector 1) which encompasses the Old City Core (Deerah highlighted in yellow) containing the traditional compact neighborhoods (Source ADA 2005).

Figure 2: Plan (left) and Aerial view (right) of the traditional core (Deerah) (Source ADA 2005).

For each neighborhood, the measures of form components were land use intensity, land use mix, street connectivity, and pedestrian accessibility. The land use intensity component includes density measures such as population and dwelling densities, average lot size, and the proportion of single-family dwelling units in each neighborhood area. Land use mix is captured in a ratio comparing the area of non-residential to residential uses. Two diversity measures are also implemented in which the proportions of multiple land use types are being compared. The street network design component includes a connectivity measure that considers street length per hectare, and street density. Other measures include block perimeter and block size to assess interconnectedness. Accessibility is measured through mean distances to the nearest commercial uses, schools, local mosques, neighborhood parks and primary health care services. Pedestrian access is captured by calculating the percentage of single-family housing units within 5 minutes' walk of the above-mentioned amenities. The following sections present the results and findings of the study and describe how measures of the above variables were computed.

As far as the subjective measures are concerned, the four main dimensions of sense of community as identified by McMillan and Chavis (1986) were evaluated. These are reinforcement, integration and fulfilment of needs, membership, influence, and shared emotional connection. Neighborhood form can either support or hamper the development of sense of community among residents by enhancing or inhibiting the establishment of these dimensions.

To measure the sense of community that a neighborhood form might foster, the sense of community index (SCI) developed by McMillan & Chavis (1986) was adopted. It consists of twelve questions covering the four dimensions above-mentioned. Each dimensions is assessed using three questions one of which is negatively worded (Table 9 below).

The study undertook a face to face interview among residents of some selected neighborhoods from both the old city (*Deerah*) and the more recently developed conventional suburban neighborhoods. The twelve items were a 5 point Likert-scale response format with statement

scores ranging from 1 “strongly disagree” to 5 “strongly agree”. The items that were negatively worded in the questionnaire were reverse coded to allow for better score comparisons between variables. The questions and the number of respondents in each city area (old and recently developed areas of Riyadh city) are reported in table 9 below. There were 149 respondents in the old city neighborhoods and 162 in the modern suburban neighborhoods.

5. Results and Findings:

The metrics used in this study to quantify neighborhood form involve the computation of neighborhood land use intensity through the use of several quantitative measures such as density measures of population and of dwelling units per unit area, lot size distribution and land use mix and diversity. The qualitative aspects of neighborhood form measures are expressed through sense of community, neighborhood walkability and sense of place assessment.

5.1. Land use intensity

Land use intensity is a determinant of neighborhood form. To capture this variable, several density measures were used such as population density (persons per hectare) and housing density (dwelling units per hectare) for each neighborhood. Table 1 below shows the mean density values for neighborhoods in both the old city and the more recently developed neighborhoods along the modern conventional suburban development (CSD) precepts.

Table 1: Land Use Intensity- Density measures

Density	Old City	Modern City
Population Density (persons/hectare)	232.3	32.6
Housing Density (dwelling unit/ha)	41.1	3.4

Figure 3: Plan view of the Old City or Deerah neighborhoods (left) and Al-Massif neighborhood (right) an example of Modern Riyadh conventional suburban development (CSD). (Source ADA 2005)

The intensity of land uses confers to the Old City or *Deerah* neighborhoods an image of compact form with higher levels of urban vibrancy. They exhibit far higher land use intensity as measured by number of residents per hectare (232 persons/ha) and housing density (41 units/ha). Modern Riyadh neighborhood forms however, show far lower intensity as their densities are only about 32 persons per hectare and 3 dwelling units per hectare respectively.

5.2. Lot size

Lot sizes of the two main land uses, residential and commercial, within a community are another intensity measure that is widely promoted by the advocates of new urbanism movement and smart growth development to achieve compact neighborhood forms. The contention is that smaller residential and commercial lots are a proxy for higher lot density and form compactness and therefore, greater land use intensity.

Here again, old Riyadh city (*Deerah*) neighborhoods show a mean value residential and commercial lot sizes of only 248.9 m² and 1554.4 m² respectively against an average of 720 m² and 1565.4 m² for the modern city. A further examination of the distribution of these lot values indicates they tend to be grouped around 100 m² for residential lots. Although the mean commercial lot size value is quite similar for both old and modern neighborhoods, their distribution in the old city reveals the existence of a considerable number of small shops of sizes not exceeding 500 m². It is precisely these small shops with varied activities that attributes an image of vibrancy and liveliness to traditional city neighborhood forms.

Table 2: Mean values of Residential & Commercial lot sizes of Riyadh neighborhoods.

Indicators	Old City	Modern City
Residential Lot Size	248.9	720.1
Commercial Lot Size	1554.4	1565.4

5.3. Land Use Mix

Land use mix and diversity of uses within a neighborhood is another descriptor of land use intensity. It is hypothesized that the more diversified the uses the more pedestrian friendly, walkable and vibrant the neighborhood would be. A form embracing diversity of uses and activities would attract people to come and experience this neighborhood vitality. Therefore, the more diversified the uses the higher the intensity of a neighborhood. The results presented in table 3 show that old city neighborhoods are much more diversified than their counterparts in the modern part of Riyadh. The fact that 57% of lots in the interstices of the modern city are still unbuilt, would adversely affect the land use intensity of its neighborhoods. On the contrary, the old city neighborhoods contain no more than 8% of undeveloped parcels. The proportion of commercial uses in the old city are more than four times what it is in the modern city (5.8% against 1.3% table3). As long as the old city neighborhoods have more developed lots and higher proportions of uses such as residential and commercial uses. This would confer to its form an image of intense and diversified activities.

This is mainly attributed to the fact that old city neighborhoods are located at the heart of the downtown commercial district. The remaining other neighborhoods in the modern part of the city lack such intensity of uses, as they are of relatively recent development and many of them tend to locate on the fringe of the city.

Table 3: Proportions of residential and commercial uses and development rate in different areas of the city.

City area	Residential		Commercial		Development	Unbuilt Parcels
Old City	9016055	27.2%	1920082	5.8%	88.38%	8%
Modern City	161378697	8.9%	25500110	1.3%	55.7%	57%

To sum up this section dealing with land use intensity, a Land-Use Mix Index (LUMI) was established as a single measure that takes into consideration the various land-uses in a

neighborhood. The Land-Use Mix Index (LUMI) is the sum of all land uses divided by the total street length in a neighborhood. The contention is that the more varied the neighborhood land-uses the higher the LUMI value and the more assorted the distribution of land uses. A high index is therefore, a proxy for land use intensity and for neighborhood form livability and vibrancy. The results indicate that the LUMI is significantly higher at the traditional neighborhoods of the old city (54.74) against only 11.1 of LUMI value in the modern area of the city (Table 4).

Table 4: The Land-Use Mix Index (LUMI) for different study areas in Riyadh

Areas	Old City	Modern City
LUMI	54.7	11.1

The data presented in table 6 below show that a person's share in residential uses is the lowest in the old city area with only 32.91 m² per person. This share increases sharply to about 1109.4 m² per person for the recently developed Riyadh neighborhoods. This suggests that Riyadh residents are likely to use excessive residential space if they happen to live in recently developed neighborhood forms than their counterparts living in the traditional old city (*Deerah*) table 5. This variable indicates that the modern city neighborhood form tends to be more sprawl-oriented whereas the old city neighborhood is a more compact form.

The share of the automobile in terms of road space is another way of capturing the sprawling characteristics of neighborhood forms. Here again, a substantial proportion of recently developed Riyadh neighborhood is reserved for car use as road space (2130.9 m² per car) table 5. The road space per car in the old city is only about 139.9 m². The explanation for this lies in the fact that the Riyadh municipality has developed the road network in many peripheral planned neighborhoods in modern Riyadh but the residential units have yet to be built up (Figure 4).

Figure 4: A Google earth view of what would be some future neighborhoods. An image very common at the outskirts of Riyadh where public services are being laid out but the private dwellings have yet to be built up (the view above from Qurtubah (left) and Al-Janadriyah (right) neighborhoods).

Table 5: Average shares of residential area per person and road area per car

City area	Land Use area per Person (m ² /Pers)	Road area per Car (m ² /Car)
Old City	32.9	139.9
Modern City	1109.4	2130.9

5.4. Street network connectivity and block size measures

Street network connectivity is another important descriptor of neighborhood form. The contention is that the greater the street connectivity the more compact the neighborhood form. By contrast, the lower the connectivity the more sprawl-oriented is that form. Overall street connectivity is computed by combining both internal and external connectivity. Internal connectivity describes transportation route options within a neighborhood. It is measured by the centerline length of local or minor streets by the neighborhood area. External connectivity on the other hand, depicts route options between neighborhoods and is measured by centerline length of main streets per unit area.

The old city neighborhoods present greater overall connectivity as measured by road network intensity (284.1 m/ha) than the modern suburban neighborhoods (54.9) (table 6). When this overall connectivity is broken down into internal and external connectivity, the old traditional neighborhoods still show much higher internal and external connectivity values than their counterparts in the modern suburban conventional development (table 6).

Table 6: Centerline street length per hectare in different study areas of Riyadh

Riyadh Areas	Interconnectedness: Street Network Density Measures					
	Main Street Length (m)	Minor Street Length (m)	Total Street Length (m)	Internal Connectivity (m /ha)	External Connectivity (m /ha)	Overall Connectivity (m /ha)
Old City	78643.2	798319	876962	258.6	25.5	284.1
Modern City	1135636	18984442	20120078	51.3	3.6	54.9

Street network connectivity at the neighborhood level depends also to a large extent on block attributes. The smaller the block size the higher the street connectivity. The old city neighborhoods have higher block density (1.7 blocks per hectare) against (0.2 blocks per hectare) in the modern city neighborhoods (table 7). When looking at the block perimeter, the *Deerah* neighborhoods have an average block perimeter of 245.1 meter against 929 meters for the modern suburban ones.

Street connectivity and block attributes are also a proxy for pedestrian accessibility and neighborhood form compactness. Compact pedestrian friendly neighborhood forms tend to have smaller block sizes and higher street connectivity. Whereas sprawling suburban neighborhoods have larger blocks and lower connectivity and are therefore, pedestrian hostile.

Table 7: Interconnectedness: Block Density Measures

City Area	Interconnectedness: Block Density Measures		
	Average Block Area (m2)	Average Block Perimeter (m)	Block Density/ha
Old City	4001.09	245.1	1.7
Modern City	173095.4	929	0.2

5.5. Measures of accessibility

Accessibility is another measure of neighborhood form. New urbanist development forms show higher accessibility than their counterparts of modern suburban conventional development forms. Pedestrian accessibility to day-to-day services like commercial establishments, primary public schools, local mosques, neighborhood parks and primary health care establishments is measured using a threshold of 5 minutes' walk (about half kilometer distance) as the "cost"

field to determine the number of households within the service area. The argument is the higher the number of households serviced by these amenities the greater the pedestrian accessibility in a neighborhood is.

Table 8: Percentage of households within walking distance of the five amenities.

City area	Amenity				
	Primary educational establishments	Commercial Services	Places of Worship	Primary Health care	Neighborhood Parks
Old City	94.7%	93.6%	99.7%	36.5%	53.7%
Modern City	11.4%	6.5%	14.6%	1.5%	4.5%

Here again, the old city neighborhoods or (*Deerah*) have higher pedestrian accessibility as indicated by the percentage of households within the thresholds set for service area walking distance. Well over ninety percent of households enjoy full amenity coverage of primary educational services (94.7%), local neighborhood mosques (99.67%) and commercial establishments such as grocery stores, eating places, and other day-to-day businesses (93.6%). By contrast, modern suburban development neighborhoods show much lower accessibility as measured by percentages of housing units at walking distance from amenities (schools 11.4%, mosques 14.6%, and commerce 6.5%) (Table 8).

5.6. Sense of community and neighborhood form

So far the physical dimension of neighborhood form has been discussed. Objective quantitative measures of variables like population and dwelling densities, land use mix, block and street network patterns were used. The discussion would not be complete without an analysis of the other component of such neighborhood form that is the social dimension. This dimension is assessed using subjective qualitative measures. It unravels how local residents perceive their neighborhood in terms of sense of community, emotional attachment and belonging to their neighborhood place, and feeling of togetherness and neighborliness.

Most residents in old city rated the sense of community in their neighborhoods quite highly, with an average score on each measure of about 3.4 out of 5. Whereas those living in the recently developed neighborhoods show an average score of 2.6 out of 5 (Table 9).

The results indicate that old city neighborhood form perform far better in establishing a sense of community among local residents than do the more recently developed suburban neighborhoods in Riyadh. Traditional compact forms of the *Deerah* area (the old city core) tend to encourage the formation of social interaction and community ties as they offer more inviting streets and better public open places. On the contrary, modern suburban places created by conventional suburban developments tend to inhibit such social networking functions as its public open spaces are mostly dominated by the car.

Old city (*Deerah*) neighborhoods represent a place where residents enter in more frequent contacts with other fellow citizens, develop social ties and build up mutual trust which facilitate the establishment of communities of interest.

Table 9: Sense of Community Index (SCI) scores in Old & Modern City Neighborhoods (SCI items adopted from McMillan & Chavis: 1986).

Sense of Community Subscale Component & Item Statement	City area	1	2	3	4	5	average score
Reinforcement of Needs	Old city						3.5
	Modern City						2.6
I think my neighborhood is a good place for me to live	Old city	15	12	57	37	28	3.3
	Modern City	35	42	45	23	17	2.7
People in this neighborhood do not share the same values. (Negatively Worded Item)*	Old city	12	18	22	45	52	3.7
	Modern City	42	57	32	16	15	2.4
My neighbors and I want the same things from this neighborhood	Old city	9	25	47	39	29	3.4
	Modern City	32	41	51	22	16	2.7
Membership	Old city						3.4
	Modern City						2.3
I can recognize most of the people who live in my neighborhood	Old city	23	15	14	55	42	3.5
	Modern City	59	46	36	14	7	2.2
I feel at home in this neighborhood	Old city	21	12	40	67	9	3.2
	Modern City	62	42	32	15	11	2.2
Very few of my neighbors know me. (Negatively Worded Item)*	Old city	18	17	20	58	36	3.5
	Modern City	51	45	31	17	18	2.4
Influence	Old city						3.3
	Modern City						2.8
I care about what my neighbors think of my actions	Old city	29	27	38	39	16	2.9
	Modern City	31	35	34	37	25	2.9
I have almost no influence over what this neighborhood is like. (Negatively Worded Item)*	Old city	21	20	29	41	38	3.4
	Modern City	45	47	25	24	21	2.6
If there is a problem in this neighborhood, people who live here can get it solved	Old city	12	14	33	65	25	3.5
	Modern City	25	34	52	29	22	2.9
Shared Emotional Connection	Old city						3.5
	Modern City						2.6
It is very important to me to live in this particular neighborhood	Old city	21	13	35	39	41	3.4
	Modern City	32	41	39	26	24	2.8
People in this neighborhood generally don't get along with each other (Negatively Worded Item)*	Old city	21	22	24	45	37	3.4
	Modern City	44	32	38	25	23	2.7
I expect to live in this neighborhood a long time	Old city	7	19	24	54	45	3.7
	Modern City	57	42	23	21	19	2.4
Total Sense of Community Score	Old city						3.4
	Modern City						2.6
Strongly disagree = 1, Strongly agree = 5							
*These variables have been reverse coded to allow for better comparisons with other variables							

6. Concluding Remarks

The paper discussed several measures of neighborhood form in Riyadh City. A neighborhood form consists of two dimensions, physical and social. The physical dimension is measured using objective quantitative measures like densities of population and dwelling units, mix of land use and street patterns. The social dimension is evaluated by use of subjective qualitative measures like the perception of the sense of community, feeling of attachment to place and mutual trust that such a form may generate among neighborhood residents.

The results indicate that the neighborhood form tend to be more compact, with more connected streets, more mixed land uses and more pedestrian friendly if it happens to be in the old city of Riyadh (*Deerah*). By contrast, neighborhood forms of the more recent conventional suburban developments show far lower density, relatively more homogeneous in land use and less connected street network and hence more pedestrian hostile.

Such differences in physical objective aspects of neighborhood forms were followed by discrepancies in the social subjective aspects of such forms. The old city neighborhood forms were found to foster higher levels of sense of community among their local residents than do neighborhood forms recently developed in line with the conventional suburban development (CSD) precepts.

From the above analysis and results, some recommendations regarding Riyadh future neighborhood form design can be set forth. The main recommendation would be to shy away from the conventional suburban development of neighborhood forms as they were designed to date. They have produced pedestrian hostile environments as they rely heavily on car movement. This does not in any case mean that grid neighborhood layouts are to be completely banned. But the larger blocks ought to be shortened, the wider roads should be skinnier, the lower density need to be higher. All these characteristics (shorter blocks, skinnier streets and higher densities) were found to be proxies for liveability and liveliness that traditional neighborhoods in the old Riyadh enjoy. These same attributes were also found to positively affect the sense of community among residents.

7. References

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